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ABSTRACTS

The proximal osteotomy and corticotomy is done in single stage. The site of proximal Osteotomy is above the nonunion where the medullary cavity is open. The whole middle fragment between corticotomy and proximal osteotomy is brought downwards gradually till it reaches below the nonunion site. In second stage, second osteotomy is done distal to nonunion site where the medullary cavity is open. Now distal fragment is rotated at the osteotomy in such a way that it unites with the new surface made by proximal osteotomy. The atrophic pathology site is bypassed and union is made between fresh surfaces of proximal and distal osteotomy.

Result: All the nine cases got united clinically and radiologically, the average union time is 6 to 7 months with 3 years follow up. No complication of refracture occurred in 3 years follow-up

Conclusion: As union is made between two new fresh surfaces, union is not a problem. Lot of exuberant callus is formed around the nonunion site decreasing the chances of any refracture. All the associated deformity are corrected usually during treatment.

O 084. Ilizarov apparatus in treatment of crural pseudoarthrosis

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Abstract Body : Aim: Pseudoarthrosis represents one of the crural fracture complications, which can be treated using several methods (DCP plates with bone graft, intramedullary nailing, etc). One of the methods used in our clinic is the Ilizarov method.

Material and methods: In Clinic for orthopaedic surgery and traumatology in Novi Sad, in period from 2005 to 2012, 49 patients with different types of crural pseudoarthrosis were treated. Average age of the patients was 42. Patients were previously treated by: plates and screws, a cast, external fixator, and intramedullary nail. We had 17 (35%) cases of hypotrophic pseudoarthrosis, 12 (24%) cases of normotrophic pseudoarthrosis, 14 (28%) cases of hypertrophic pseudoarthrosis and 6 (13%) cases of neoarthrosis. We used monolocal closed compression osteosynthesis in 24 (49%) cases, monolocal open compression osteosynthesis in 8 (16%) cases, monolocal closed compression-distractional osteosynthesis in 9 (19%) cases, monolocal synchronous compression-distractional osteosynthesis in 8 (16%) cases.

Results: Average treatment period was 5 (4-6) months. Complete recovery was recorded in 46 (94 %) cases whereas in 3 (6%) cases the device had to be reapplied due to infection. We analyzed bone parameters and functional parameters. Bone parameters show that in 28 (58%) cases the results were excellent, in 11 (22%) cases good, in 7 (14%) cases medium, in 3 (6%) cases the results were unsatisfactory. Functional parameters show that in 30 (62%) cases the results were excellent, in 11 (22%) cases good, in 4 (8%) cases medium, in 4 (8%) cases the results were unsatisfactory.

Conclusion: Our experience confirms that treatment by the Ilizarov apparatus for transosseous osteosynthesis is a reliable method for treating crural fracture complications such as pseudoarthrosis.